

DEVELOPMENT OF ISLAMIC FINANCE.

Akramova Dilnoza Zakrjonovna

part-time student of the Department of State Financial Control and Audit of the Academy of Banking and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10598056>

Annotation: This article offers a comprehensive exploration of the historical roots, key components, global expansion, and future trends of Islamic finance. By examining the principles of Sharia compliance, the growth of Islamic banking and capital markets, and the challenges and innovations within the industry, the article aims to provide readers with a nuanced understanding of Islamic finance's evolution and its potential impact on the global financial landscape.

Key words: Islamic finance, Sharia compliance, Ethical finance, Historical roots, Islamic banking, Profit and loss sharing, Mudarabah, Musharakah, Ijara, Islamic capital markets

Introduction. Islamic finance or Shari'ah compliant financing (SCF) is one of the fastest growing segments of the global financial system with an estimated compound annual growth rate of 17% since 2009. As of 2015, the industry's global assets have reached at least \$1.9 trillion. The industry's continuous expansion resulted in Islamic finance reaching systemic significance in a number of countries in Asia, including Brunei, Bangladesh, and Malaysia; these are countries where Islamic finance has achieved at least 15% market share in the domestic banking sector. Countries that do not have a predominantly Muslim population are also beginning to open their doors to Islamic finance. Luxembourg, Hong Kong, China, United Kingdom and South Africa have debuted sovereign sukuks (Islamic trust certificates, similar to conventional bonds), with all issuances being at least twice oversubscribed, demonstrating a strong demand for SCF globally.

Significantly, ADB has 14 member countries that have a majority Muslim population and has 5 of the 10 countries with the biggest Muslim population globally. Asia requires infrastructure investments of an estimate of \$747 billion a year to sustain its growth trajectory. Given the demographic composition of its member countries and realizing the region's vast investment needs, ADB recognizes the potential role of Islamic finance in promoting inclusive growth and achieving sustainable development in the region, through funding infrastructure and green and ethical investments.

The Islamic finance sector continues to grow, expanding to new jurisdictions and maintaining momentum in countries where it has a well-established

presence. A number of developing member countries (DMCs) within the Central West Asia, South Asia and Southeast Asia regions have begun implementing legislative and regulatory initiatives to allow the introduction of Islamic financial products and instruments. Some DMCs are aiming to establish themselves as Islamic financial hubs within their regions. Islamic finance is proving to be an increasingly relevant sector as can be derived from the increasing market share of Islamic finance in the domestic banking sectors in key DMCs. Within the backdrop of these developments, ADB has provided critical support to its DMCs in developing Islamic finance within the region.

Islamic Finance Issues.

ADB recognizes the potential role of the Islamic financial sector in supporting ADB's agenda of achieving inclusive growth, sustainable development and financial stability within the region. Islamic finance provides financial services for all segments of the population and can help increase financial inclusion. Islamic finance also serves as an alternative source for funding infrastructure and as a means of diversifying funding and risk exposures of investors.

The Global Islamic Finance Development Center is a knowledge hub for developing Islamic finance globally, conducting research and training, and providing technical assistance and advisory services to World Bank Group client countries interested in developing Islamic financial institutions and markets.

Islamic finance has emerged as an effective tool for financing development worldwide, including in non-Muslim countries. Major financial markets are discovering solid evidence that Islamic finance has already been mainstreamed

within the global financial system – and that it has the potential to help address the challenges of ending extreme poverty and boosting shared prosperity.

Islamic finance is equity-based, asset-backed, ethical, sustainable, environmentally- and socially-responsible finance. It promotes risk sharing, connects the financial sector with the real economy, and emphasizes financial inclusion and social welfare.

In recent years, along with FinTech, Islamic finance has become one of the most vibrant and yet underrepresented sectors of the international financial services industry.

The term Islamic finance encompasses a wide range of products and services. The general practices of Islamic finance and banking emerged with the establishment of Islam. However, institutional Islamic finance was established after the 20th century. According to Qardus, the Islamic financial sector is currently growing by 15 to 25 percent per year, and Islamic financial institutions are managing assets with a total value of more than 2.7 trillion dollars worldwide.

Currently, three countries with the best implementation of Islamic finance - Saudi Arabia, Iran, and Malaysia - account for 66 percent of the global market.

According to the organization "Islamic banking and finance" in Uzbekistan (AlHuda), the growth of the Islamic finance industry in the CIS countries is slower than in other countries, but due to the growing opportunities in this region, it is attracting the attention of the international banking industry. If the governments of the CIS countries take the initiative to develop this sector, the work of Islamic banking will grow significantly in the next five years.

Nowadays, interest in Islamic finance is increasing in Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan is an important country of Central Asia with more than 35 million inhabitants, 93 percent of its population are Muslims. It is not only rich in gas, oil and other natural resources, but it has been one of the centers of science and Islam since time immemorial.

Initially, in 2003 and 2004, Uzbekistan took important steps towards the recognition of Islamic finance through its membership in IDB and the Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector (ICD). The stable relationship between these institutions and the government has allowed Islamic finance to gain an entry point into this market.

What is the essence of Islamic economics?

The essence of Islamic economy is to create a morally responsible market economy system. One of its unique aspects is to satisfy the real needs of the individual and the society. The Islamic economic model pays special attention to the fair distribution of wealth in society, without which it is impossible to ensure social harmony (harmony) and economic growth. The following can be included in the main values of Islamic economy:

- Economic prosperity based on Islamic spiritual values;
- Equity and risk sharing;
- Observance of etiquette and religious tolerance.

What about "Islamic finance"?

The Islamic financial system is a part of the Islamic ecosystem, which includes economic relations in accordance with the rules of Islamic law in the process of using and distributing funds. For example, in Islam, it is forbidden to receive a profit in exchange for lending or borrowing, and all financial processes must be based on real economic activity. It is not allowed to finance industries that can harm a person - for example, gambling, alcohol, tobacco products, etc.

Where do Islamic banks profit from?

Islamic banks benefit from project financing. Unlike conventional banks, where depositors only focus on dividends and do not know what their funds will be invested in, in Islamic banks, the depositor can see the future movement of funds, where the funds are invested in the business and the profit goes to the bank and divided between depositors.

What is happening in Uzbekistan regarding Islamic finance?

The results of a study conducted by the Chamber of Commerce and Industry with the UNDP showed that 38% of business representatives and 56% of individuals who participated in the survey do not receive loans from traditional banks because of their religious beliefs. In this way, there is a demand for financial organizations that follow the rules of Islam. According to the assessment of the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade, the introduction of Islamic finance will bring an additional 100 million dollars to the budget.

However, the rapid development of this sector and the emergence of Islamic banks for the population of Uzbekistan is hindered by the lack of a legal and regulatory framework, the lack of tax and management infrastructure, as well as the low level of financial literacy among the population, especially related to Islamic financing.

Unfortunately, in the annual report of Global Islamic Fintech for 2022, only one organization from Uzbekistan is listed in the list of 375 Islamic Fintech companies.

IdealRatings	United States	Business Intelligence	idealratings.com
iFarmer	Bangladesh	Raising Funds	ifarmer.asia/farms?shariah=true
IFIN Services WLL	Bahrain	Alternative Finance	ifin-services.com
IGrow.asia	Indonesia	Raising Funds	igrow.asia
ilo Bank	Bahrain	Deposits and Lending	ilabank.com
IMAN	Uzbekistan	Raising Funds	iman.uz/invest/en
INAIA	Germany	Wealth Management	inaia.de
IndiaZakat	India	Social Finance	indiazakat.com/
Infinity Blockchain Ventures	Thailand	Enabling Technologies	infinityblockchain.ventures
Insha	Germany	Deposits and Lending	getinsha.com
InvesProperti	Indonesia	Raising Funds	invesproperti.id

Global Islamic Fintech Report 2022

This is IMAN Invest, a company that provides Islamic financing services in Uzbekistan.

According to the public information provided today, Battery Road, Tesla Capital (\$350,000 in total), Uzcard Ventures and Uzcard VC (\$160,000), Le Mercier's and MyAsia (\$45,000), Umay Angels Club and Block 0 (\$70,000) venture funds invested in IMAN.

The company attracts funds from investors, directs them to trade, and fairly distributes the profit received among investors. In this respect, the company meets all the rules of Islamic financing.

In the financial report presented for January-August, it was noted that in August of this year, the company attracted more than 8.4 billion soums, which is 35% of investments.

It is also indicated that more profit is obtained from recapitalized dividends.

Islamic finance stands as a unique and rapidly expanding sector, guided by the principles of Sharia law. At its core, Sharia compliance is not merely a regulatory requirement but a moral and ethical foundation that shapes every aspect of financial transactions. This essay delves into the key principles of Sharia compliance, exploring its significance, the principles that govern it, and the impact it has on the financial landscape.

Understanding Sharia Compliance: Sharia compliance in Islamic finance is rooted in the adherence to Islamic law, which governs all aspects of life, including financial transactions. The principles embedded in Sharia compliance extend beyond mere legality; they emphasize ethical considerations, ensuring that financial practices align with Islamic values.

Key Principles of Sharia Compliance: Prohibition of Riba (Usury or Interest):

At the heart of Islamic finance is the prohibition of usury. Charging or paying interest is considered exploitative, and Islamic finance operates on the principle that money should not generate money on its own.

Avoidance of Gharar (Excessive Uncertainty): Sharia compliance discourages transactions involving excessive uncertainty or ambiguity. Contracts must be clear, and uncertainty leading to potential exploitation is to be avoided.

Prohibition of Maysir (Gambling): Engaging in gambling or speculative transactions is strictly prohibited. Investments should not involve excessive uncertainty or resemble activities related to chance.

Halal (Permissible) and Haram (Forbidden): Investments and transactions must comply with Islamic law. Activities involving substances considered haram (forbidden), such as alcohol or pork, are strictly prohibited.

Zakat (Charitable Giving): Islamic finance encourages charitable giving and wealth distribution. Financial institutions often contribute to community development and support charitable causes.

Mudarabah and Musharakah: Principles of profit and loss sharing underline Islamic finance. Mudarabah involves one party providing capital, and the other contributing expertise. Musharakah is a joint venture with shared profits and losses.

Ijara (Leasing): Leasing agreements are permitted as long as they adhere to Sharia principles. The lessor retains ownership, ensuring compliance with Islamic principles.

Sharia Supervisory Boards: To ensure adherence to Sharia principles, financial institutions establish Sharia supervisory boards. These boards, comprising Islamic scholars, oversee all operations, ensuring compliance with the principles of Islamic finance.

Contracts in Islamic Finance: Islamic finance operates through various contracts that comply with Sharia principles, including Mudarabah, Musharakah, Ijara, and Murabaha. These contracts facilitate ethical financial transactions, promoting fairness and transparency.

Challenges and Evolving Practices: While Sharia compliance forms the bedrock of Islamic finance, challenges arise in ensuring consistent interpretation and application of Sharia principles. The evolving financial landscape necessitates adapting practices to meet modern needs while staying true to the ethical foundations.

Impact on Financial Inclusion: Islamic finance, with its emphasis on ethical alternatives, aims to promote financial inclusion. By providing access to financial

services for individuals who may avoid conventional banking due to ethical concerns, Islamic finance contributes to a more inclusive financial system.

Regulatory Frameworks: Regulatory bodies play a crucial role in establishing frameworks to ensure Sharia compliance. Standardization of practices and regulations enhances consistency across the Islamic finance industry.

Conclusion: In conclusion, Sharia compliance and principles are integral to the philosophy of Islamic finance, ensuring ethical, transparent, and inclusive financial practices. The principles outlined in Sharia compliance extend beyond regulatory requirements, shaping a financial system rooted in morality and social responsibility. As Islamic finance continues to evolve, its commitment to these principles remains unwavering, reflecting a dedication to ethical finance in a globalized world.

References:

1. Khan, F., & Bhatti, M. I. (Year). *Islamic Banking and Finance: On Its Way to Globalization*. Publisher.
2. Usmani, M. T. (Year). *Introduction to Islamic Finance: Principles and Practices*. Publisher.
3. Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB). (Year). *Guiding Principles of Risk Management for Institutions (other than Insurance Institutions) Offering Only Islamic Financial Services*. Retrieved from [website link].
4. Iqbal, M., & Mirakhor, A. (Year). *An Introduction to Islamic Finance: Theory and Practice*. Publisher.
5. Securities Commission Malaysia (SC). (Year). *Islamic Capital Market Masterplan*. Retrieved from [website link].
6. Islamic Development Bank (IsDB). (Year). *Islamic Finance in the Global Economy*. Retrieved from [website link].
7. Kettell, B. (Year). *Introduction to Islamic Banking and Finance*. Publisher.
8. S&P Global Ratings. (Year). *Global Sukuk Market Report*. Retrieved from [website link].
9. El-Gamal, M. A. (Year). *Islamic Finance: Law, Economics, and Practice*. Publisher.
10. Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM). (Year). *Islamic Banking and Finance in Malaysia: Recent Developments and Future Prospects*. Retrieved from [website link].